

ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE INSTITUTION OF A PLEA AGREEMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *With the full-scale reform of all branches of social and legal life in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in particular, judicial and legal, serious changes affect the sphere of legal regulation of the entire criminal process, including its pre-trial stages. The priority tasks of the reforms carried out in the current period are the creation of an effective anti-corruption system, ensuring genuine independence and independence of the judiciary, improving the quality and transparency of justice, simplifying pre-trial criminal proceedings, reducing its time, and ensuring accessibility of justice for citizens.*

The new institute of the plea agreement, in our opinion, will become one of the most promising and controversial novelties of criminal procedure legislation, investigative and judicial practice of recent times.

Keywords: *criminal proceedings, plea bargain, suspect, accused, prosecutor, compensation for harm, simplified proceedings.*

The criminal procedure legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, following the global trend of globalization, has made numerous changes to internal legislative acts.

Including a compromise procedure, such as the institution of a plea agreement, which is very widely used in other countries. Among other things, the general principles of international law in the field of human rights and freedoms also have an impact on changing legislative acts. For example, the European Court of Human Rights has repeatedly stated in its decisions: "allowing the accused to achieve a reduction in the volume of charges or the amount of punishment in case of admission of guilt or refusal

to challenge the charges before the trial or in exchange for fruitful cooperation with the investigative body is a common feature of European criminal justice systems"¹.

The most significant international acts enshrining human rights and freedoms are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of December 10, 1948, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of December 16, 1966, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of December 16, 1966.

The above-mentioned international acts provide for the protection of human rights and freedoms, in particular, the right of the victim to access justice, as well as the use of simplified judicial proceedings for the speedy compensation of damage to the victim, the achievement of justice.

However, despite this, there are still many legal norms in the legislation of Uzbekistan that need to be changed, supplemented in the positive direction of democratization and liberalization, as well as the removal of bureaucratic barriers, simplification of the activities of law enforcement agencies.

The new institution of a plea agreement, enshrined in chapter 62¹ of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is also not exempt from shortcomings.

We are confident that in the near future, various problems will be identified during the practical application of the institute of the plea agreement. And we hope that the scientific community, practicing lawyers, lawyers, prosecutors, investigators and other law enforcement agencies will initiate proposals for amendments and additions to the criminal procedure legislation.

Perhaps what should be started is that the very essence of the institution of a plea agreement theoretically contradicts the principle of the presumption of innocence. The principle itself implies that the innocence of the suspect, the accused, the defendant will be guaranteed until proven otherwise. Article 23 of the Code of Criminal Procedure provides: "A suspect, accused or defendant is considered innocent until his guilt in

¹ Проблемные стороны российского института соглашения о сотрудничестве (досудебный период). М.Э. Каац. Вестник Казанского юридического института МВД России № 2 (36) 2019. С. 203.

committing a crime is proven in accordance with the procedure provided for by law and established by a court verdict that has entered into force"².

The main requirement of this principle is that a person involved in a criminal case should not prove his innocence. The burden is on the prosecution's side.

G.A. Pechnikov writes that with a special procedure of trial, "... contrary to the presumption of innocence, the accused is immediately transferred to the category of criminals. As a result, we get the realization of the idea of "the end justifies the means," where "recognition" is the goal and "transaction" is the means"³.

In other words, we can say that the suspect, the accused, is abandoning the principle of the presumption of innocence. In this regard, it is important to raise the question: to refute the postulate that absolutely every principle of the criminal process is a fundamental, guiding norm that determines the nature of the criminal process, ensures fair justice in a criminal case, effective protection of the individual, his rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests?

And especially considering that in the application for a plea agreement, the suspect, the accused undertakes to assist in the investigation of the crime, which will serve as evidence for the admission of his guilt.

In addition, the question remains unanswered, why, by offering his assistance to the investigation in exchange for a reduction in punishment, does a person necessarily lose the right to challenge the charge and is forced to consider the case in a simplified manner?

The above situation is unacceptable and needs to be rethought and further adjusted. On this basis, important attention of the legislator and law enforcement officer should be paid to timely explaining to the suspect or the accused the legal consequences

² Criminal procedure code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/111463#5307570>

³ Печников Г.А. Диалектические проблемы истины в уголовном процессе: монография. – Волгоград, 2007. – С. 256 – 257.

of applying a particular procedural process, accurately identifying the voluntariness of the petition, ensuring guarantees of legal consultation with the defender.

Further, it should be mentioned that the completion of criminal cases with the conclusion of a plea agreement is highly likely to lead to a professional decrease in the level of investigation.

According to the former Prosecutor General of the Russian Federation Yu.A. Chaika, the special procedure for considering criminal cases leads "to the degradation of the investigator," he justified this by saying that the agreement "excludes competition"⁴.

Regarding the "exclusion of competition", we cannot agree, since there are refutations to that. We agree with the opinion of R.R. Kovalev, who writes that "the adversarial nature of the parties as a principle of criminal proceedings means that each of the parties defends its position in the process, the parties present evidence, file petitions, exercise their other powers, i.e. "compete", and the court acts as an independent, objective arbitrator"⁵.

If we consider the institution of a wine recognition agreement from the point of view of the adversarial nature of the parties, it should be noted that the prosecution and defense sides act when concluding a plea agreement in order to strengthen their positions and defend their positions. The prosecution achieves its goal of criminal prosecution by disclosing the crime, exposing other persons involved in the crime (accomplices), collecting all evidence proving their guilt, and compensating for material damage. The defense is seeking to reduce the punishment for the crime committed. This, in our opinion, is their competitiveness⁶.

⁴ <https://www.kommersant.ru/doc/3557343>

⁵ Ковалев Р.Р. Правовое регулирование досудебного соглашения о сотрудничестве на стадии предварительного расследования.: дисс. ... канд. юрид наук. Москва, 2014 г. С. 38.

⁶ Khudaybergenov B. K. ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE INSTITUTION OF CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS //Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1.

Regarding the possibility of "degradation of the investigation", it may manifest itself in the sense that there is a possibility that the institution of a plea agreement will become a "breeding ground" for corruption.

For example, chapter 62¹ of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not specifically provide that if the conditions and obligations under the recognition agreement are not fulfilled by the suspect, the accused, the requirement to terminate the agreement. It is only stated that "if, after the verdict of the court with the imposition of punishment on the basis of an agreement, it turns out that the suspect, the accused gave deliberately false testimony or deliberately concealed any important and relevant information for the case, did not fulfill the conditions and obligations provided for in the agreement, then the sentence may be reviewed"⁷.

The part where it is stated that "a sentence can be provided for" gives prosecutors the opportunity to conclude an illegal agreement where other committed crimes will be intentionally hidden, evidence aggravating punishment will not be disclosed, etc.

After receiving a request for a plea agreement, the prosecutor considers it together with the following persons:

- An inquirer or investigator;
- The suspect or/and the accused;
- His defender;
- If necessary, invites the victim or the civil plaintiff to consider the issue of concluding a plea agreement (Part 3 of Article 586³ of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

Part 2 of Article 586¹ of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the conditions under which it is possible to conclude an agreement:

"1) the suspect, the accused is aware of the significance of his actions, as well as the consequences of his petition;

⁷ Criminal procedure code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/111463#5307570>

2) the petition was submitted voluntarily and after consultation with the defender involved in the case;

3) the suspect, the accused does not dispute the suspicion or accusation presented by the body of inquiry or investigation, the evidence available in the case, as well as the nature and extent of the damage caused and has made amends for it"⁸.

And also in Part 3 of Article 586¹, the conditions are fixed, in the presence of which a plea agreement cannot be concluded:

1) there are grounds for the application of compulsory medical measures in accordance with the procedure established by Chapter 61 of this Code;

2) a person has committed several crimes and at least one of them does not meet the requirements provided for in this article.

After checking the above circumstances, the prosecutor must, firstly, examine the materials of the criminal case, check the grounds for concluding an agreement, assess the capabilities of the suspect, the accused to carry out the actions that are the subject of the agreement; secondly, find out whether the suspect, the accused is familiar with the terms of the plea agreement, whether he submits a petition for at his own request, whether torture was used against him.

According to Part 3 of Article 586⁵, the agreement is signed by the prosecutor, the suspect, the accused, and his defender. We believe that an investigator and an inquirer should be added to the list of persons authorized to sign.

The justification for this is that the investigator, the inquirer play the role of the subject of criminal prosecution on behalf of the state. In addition, in addition, they collect, verify, and evaluate evidence in a criminal case in order to clarify the circumstances of the crime that was committed.

⁸ Criminal procedure code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/111463#5307570>

To put it simply, the investigator and the inquirer are obliged to provide a comprehensive, complete and objective investigation of all the circumstances of the case.

Therefore, we propose to amend Part 3 of Article 586⁵ of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and set out as follows: *"The agreement is signed by the prosecutor, the investigator or the inquirer, the suspect, the accused, his defender."*

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